

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF POST-VIRAL SYNDROME: A CLINICAL CASE AND SAIDDHANTIKA REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Background: Post-Viral Syndrome (PVS) is a debilitating condition characterized by persistent fatigue, musculoskeletal pain, neuropathic discomfort, sleep disturbances, and cognitive impairments that linger beyond the resolution of acute viral infections. In modern medicine, management remains largely symptomatic and supportive, with limited curative options. In Ayurveda, such residual manifestations are interpreted through the lens of *Vataj Jwara* and its *Upadravas*. **Case & Intervention:** A 46 years old female, with complains of the fatigue, calf muscles pain, disturbed sleep, lower back pain, anorexia and heaviness in the body from last 2-3 months seeking for Ayurveda treatment for the same. She under goes with the *Ayurvedic* management by oral medication and *Pathya Palan*. **Outcome:** After 2 months of treatment, she recovers from her all complains. **Conclusion:** Ayurvedic therapy effectively resolves Post-Viral Syndrome (PVS).

KEYWORDS: Post-Viral Syndrome (PVS), *Vataj Jwara*, *Upadravas*, *Trividha Bodhya Samghrah*.

INTRODUCTION

Post-viral syndrome is a wide range of complex conditions involving physical, cognitive, emotional and neurological difficulties that vary in severity over time. These conditions frequently lead to a sense of tiredness and weakness, pain, difficulty concentrating and headaches that linger after the viral infection has cleared. Symptoms may continue for weeks, months or longer. While post-viral syndrome may appear similar to other health issues, it is important to exclude other conditions to have a clear understanding of the problem. Post-viral syndrome is triggered by a reaction to a virus which does not resolve in the normal way but continues in the form of sustained inflammation. Various microbial and viral infections are possible trigger factors for post-viral syndrome, including Epstein-Barr virus, cytomegalovirus, human herpesvirus, enteroviruses, Lyme disease, Covid-19 and more. For patients, a sense of fatigue persists regardless of rest or additional sleep. Painkillers are often prescribed for aches and pains. Patients are advised to conserve energy, practice stress management techniques and eat a healthy diet. The jury is currently out regarding the benefits of exercise, with many individuals reporting a worsening of symptoms. Many viral infections can trigger post-viral syndrome, with individuals who have weakened immune systems appearing to be at heightened risk. It remains unclear why the effects of a virus can linger in the body. Some theories suggest that the virus 'overloads' the immune system, preventing healthy immune system resolution for weeks, months or years.^[1]

From an Ayurvedic perspective, this condition correlates with *Vataja Jwara* and its *Upadravas* (complications). Symptoms observed in this case study—such as *Pindikodweshtana* (cramping pain in the calf muscles), *Ashyavairasyata* (altered taste perception), *Shrama* (fatigue), *Pipasa* (excessive thirst), *Katiparshwaprustha shool* (Lower back pain) and *Prajagara* (insomnia) etc.^[2]—are consistent with the classical descriptions of *Vataja Jwara*.

METHODOLOGY

Case report

A 46-year-old female patient with a history of COVID-19 infection and subsequent treatment presented with complaints of persistent fatigue (*Shrama*), calf muscle pain (*Pindikodweshtana*), disturbed sleep (*Prajagara/Alpa Nidra*), Lower back ache (*Parshva-Kati Shoola*) and a sense of heaviness (*Gauravta*) in the body for the past 2–3 months. She had previously consulted a nearby allopathic practitioner and was prescribed medication that

provided temporary symptomatic relief. However, the symptoms recurred upon discontinuation of the medication.

Clinical findings

General examination

Decreased appetite and sleep, constipated bowel, regular micturition, Vitals were normal.

Laboratory investigation

In CBC report HB was found low (8g/dL) (Image.1)

Timelines of events

Table 1: Represent the timeline of the disease.

Date of Visit	Findings	Intervention
28.09.2021	fatigue, calf muscles pain, disturbed sleep, lower back pain, anorexia and heaviness in the body	Tab. <i>Vaishvanar</i> Tab. <i>Kalingadi</i> Tab. <i>Anushiva</i> DTH (<i>Dwatrishat kwath</i>) <i>Kwath</i>
13.10.2021	Fatigue, calf muscles pain, disturbed sleep and lower back pain	Tab. <i>Vaishvanar</i> Tab. <i>Kalingadi</i> Tab. <i>Anushiva</i>
10.11.2021	lower back pain	Tab. <i>Trayodashang Guggulu</i> Tab. <i>Anushiva</i>
10.12.2021	Decreased lower back pain	Tab. <i>Trayodashang Guggulu</i> Tab. <i>Anushiva</i>
23.12.2021	-	Stop medication
20.01.2022	-	-

Therapeutic Intervention

The patient had not taken any Allopathic medicines. Then we give her Ayurvedic intervention. She was prescribed the following medication with required changes for 3 months.

Table 2: List of internal medicine with their possible effects.

Medicine	Dose	Time of administration	Duration	Possible effect
Tab. <i>Vaishvanar</i>	2 tablets with water	Morning, Noon and Evening before meal	45 days	<i>Dipan and Pachan</i>
Tab. <i>Kalingadi</i>	2 tablets with water	Morning, Noon and Evening before meal	45 days	<i>Rasdustihara</i>
Tab. <i>Anushiva</i>	3 tablets with water	At Night	75 days	<i>Doshanuloman</i>

DTH (<i>Dwattrinshat Kwath</i>) <i>Kwath</i>	50ml <i>Kwath</i>	Morning and evening before meal	15 days	<i>Jwarghna and Doshanuloman</i>
Tab. <i>Trayodashang Guggulu</i>	2 tablets with water	Morning, Noon and Evening before meal	60 days	<i>Kledahara and Asthidhatu poshaka</i>

Table 3: List of diet and regimen followed by patient.

Diet	Regimen
<p><i>Poha or upma or murmura or khakhara</i> with tea in breakfast. Dala-rich, green gram, rock salt. Vegetables- bottle gourd, bitter gourd, pumpkin, cucumber, ridge gourd, pointed gourd, spiny gourd, eggplant etc. Cow milk, Ghee, buttermilk with cumin powder. Fruits- pomegranate, Indian gooseberry, grapes, dates. Cumin seeds after meal.</p>	<p>Sleep for 6-7 h at night. Walking or <i>Suryanamaskar</i> in morning for 45 min Avoid day sleep Avoid Mental stress</p>

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

After the initial 14 days of treatment, the patient experienced relief from anorexia and a sense of heaviness in the body. By the 45th day of treatment, all complaints had resolved except for lower back pain, which was completely cured after an additional one month of therapy. At the one-month follow-up, no recurrence of symptoms was observed and haemoglobin increased HB=11.5g/dL. (Image. 2)

DISCUSSION

Samprapti (pathophysiology)

The patient presented with symptoms such as *Shrama* (fatigue), *Pindikodweshtana* (calf muscle pain), *Prajagara/Alpa Nidrata* (disturbed sleep), *Parshva-Kati Shoola* (lower back pain), *Aruchi* (anorexia), and *Gauravata* (heaviness in the body), which are indicative of *Vataja Jwara Lakshana*. Additionally, some symptoms correspond to the features of *Rasa Pradoshaja Vyadhi*. Following COVID-19 treatment, there was no proper elimination of the aggravated *Doshas* from the body. These accumulated *Doshas* became *Leena Dosha* and led to *Srotorodha*, primarily affecting the *Rasavaha Srotas*. This obstruction resulted in a decreased *Rasa Bhag* of *Aahara Rasa* reaching the successive *Dhatus*. Such a condition can be considered as an *Upadrava* (complication) of *Jwara*, or may manifest as various *Rasa Pradoshaja Vyadhis*, such as *Pandu*.

Samprapti-ighatan

In Ayurveda, *Samprapti Vighatana* refers to the breakdown of the pathogenesis of a disease. The first step is *Nidana Parivarjana*, achieved by prescribing a diet that halts further progression of the disease. The medicines used included *Jwarahara* and *Doshanulomana* formulations. Tab. *Vaishvara* possesses *Dipana* and *Pachana* properties, which enhance digestion and help metabolize undigested food. Tab. *Kalingadi* and *DTH Kwath* exhibit *Jwarahara* (antipyretic) properties, primarily acting on the *Rasa Dhatu*. Tab. *Anushiva* has *Doshanulomana* (eliminative) properties, aiding in the expulsion of vitiated *Doshas*. Tab. *Trayodashanga Guggulu* is *Kledaghna* and nourishes the *Asthi Dhatu*. From the *Saindhnatika* perspective, the treatment protocol can be understood through the lens of *Trividh Bodhya Samgraha*. Among the medicines, Tab. *Vaishvara*, Tab. *Kalingadi*, Tab. *Anushiva*, and *DTH Kwath* contribute to *Vikara Prakriti Vighatana*, i.e., *Samprapti Vighatana*. Tab. *Anushiva* and Tab. *Trayodashanga Guggulu* act on the *Vikara Adhithana*, i.e., *Prakriti Sthapana*. Meanwhile, *Nidana Parivarjana* (diet and regimen) addresses the *Vikara Samutthana*.

CONCLUSION

As per *Acharya Charaka* in the *Charaka Samhita*, it is not shameful if a competent *Vaidya* does not know the name of a disease. By applying the principle of *Trividh Bodhya Sangraha*^[3], the physician should understand the *Vikara Samutthana* (etiology), *Vikara Prakriti* (nature of the disease), and *Vikara Adhithana* (site of manifestation). Through the knowledge of this principle, the *Vaidya* should never fail in *Chikitsa* (treatment).

Patient perspective

“I had complaints of persistent fatigue, calf muscle pain, disturbed sleep, and a sense of heaviness in the body, with an initial haemoglobin level of 8 g/dL. I took allopathic medicines but did not experience significant relief. Therefore, I started Ayurvedic treatment and followed the prescribed dietary regimen for three months. As a result, I achieved complete relief from all my complaints, and my haemoglobin level improved to 11.5 g/dL after treatment.”

Image. 1

Image. 2

REFERENCES

1. SMA-An Overview of Post-viral Syndrome August 16, 2021 // Randy Glick
2. Acharya Y. T, editor Charak Samhita by Agnivesha, Nidanasthana, Jwarnidana, Reprint edition Varanasi: Chakhambha Publication: 2023: 200.
3. Acharya Y. T, editor Charak Samhita by Agnivesha, Sutrasthana, Trishothiya Adhyaya, Reprint edition Varanasi: Chakhambha Publication: 2023: 108.